

Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

D7.1: Stakeholder Engagement Strategy Plan and Annual Reports

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Abbreviations / Definitions

ACT4CAP27	Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
MS	Member State
NGOs	Non-governmental organisations
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Work Package (WP) 7 'Stakeholder Engagement and Dissemination' in ACT4CAP27 (Advancing Capacity and Analytical Tools for Supporting Common Agricultural Policies post-2027) is dedicated to maintain a continuous dialogue with policymakers at the EU and Member State (MS) level, as well as other relevant stakeholders. Additionally, WP7 aims to maximise the visibility of the project among target audiences and ensure the effective exploitation of project results, extending even beyond the implementation of the project.

Within WP7, Ecorys leads Task 7.1, which specifically focuses on stakeholder engagement. The establishment of the ACT4CAP27 Stakeholder and Dissemination Platform, also referred to as the ACT4CAP27 Platform, will therein play a crucial role in sharing and discussing the outcomes of ACT4CAP27 with existing model platforms, research communities and policy makers. This will allow the integration of a diversity of stakeholder visions on, for example, the development of the possible future scenarios (baseline and alternative futures) which will be developed over the course of the project.

This deliverable D7.1 'Stakeholder Engagement Strategy Plan and Annual Reports' outlines the objectives of the Stakeholder Engagement and Dissemination Platform, detailing the strategy of effectively identifying and engaging stakeholders within ACT4CAP27, as well as the annual reporting on stakeholder engagement activities.

1. INTRODUCTION

ACT4CAP27 is a European research project coordinated by Wageningen Research (WR). It gathers 13 partner organisations to enhance analytical capabilities, tools, and collaborative technical infrastructure within the policy modelling community to support evidence-based European Union (EU) agri-food policies post-2027. The project adopts a comprehensive food system approach, focusing on building analytical capacity for the quantitative assessment of the impacts of upcoming agri-food policies on the economic, social (including health), environmental, and climate sustainability of food systems.

The project's specific objectives include:

- Designing a conceptual data and modelling framework to understand and improve EU food system performance, and assess policy impact. (WP1, WP6)
- Developing a modular toolbox to quantify the transition to a sustainable EU food system and its societal contributions. (WP2, WP3)
- Ensuring the adoption and evolution of the toolbox while fostering community building. (WP4, WP5)
- Establishing a platform for stakeholder interaction and dialogues at different stages of the project. (WP7)

This deliverable will mainly focus on the last objective, demonstrating the role of the Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform in ACT4CAP27 in bringing together experts from different policy areas and sectors to collaboratively shape the outputs of the project. Through this multidisciplinary approach, we hope to actively strengthen the interaction between science and policy, thereby contributing to better informed decision-making, broader societal engagement and innovation in governance, and breaking down silo thinking.

Therefore, the main objective of this deliverable D7.1 'Stakeholder Engagement Strategy Plan and Annual Reports' is to outline a strategy for stakeholder engagement in ACT4CAP27 to ensure effective collaboration, communication and involvement of key stakeholders throughout the project. The first section of this deliverable will provide an in-depth look at the ACT4CAP27 platform and its objectives. We will then outline the target audience we intend to engage through this platform. Finally, we will provide an overview of the planned stakeholder activities, explain how we will report on their outcomes through annual reports and how we foresee to improve on stakeholder engagement throughout the project.

2. OBJECTIVES

The ACT4CAP27 Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform is structured around three core methodological pillars: 'Designing & Assessing' (Pillar 1), 'Modelling' (Pillar 2), and 'Safeguarding' (Pillar 3) (see Figure 1). Together, these pillars provide a robust framework for achieving the project's four specific objectives (see Introduction), with the Platform acting as the central component to support and integrate these efforts.

Figure 1. The Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform based on three pillars

Pillar 1 is focused on defining and operationalising the performance of the EU food system. This includes identifying determinants and outcomes, as well as generating evidence on cause-and-effect relationships. This pillar establishes a conceptual data and modelling framework, identifies gaps in current tools for assessing the impact of agri-food policies, and provides guidance on subsequent model and data improvements (WP1). It will also produce an ACT4CAP27 Interactive Roadmap, a strategic guide to assess EU agri-food policies post 2027 to advance EU food systems towards enhanced sustainability, inclusivity and climate resilience (WP6).

Pillar 2 is dedicated to model-based analysis of EU food systems, with the development of the ACT4CAP27 Modular Toolbox for Sustainable Food System Policy Modelling. It extends existing models to cover economic, social, environmental and climate sustainability aspects to improve the representation of EU food systems and strengthen policy impact assessments in these areas (WP2, WP3).

Pillar 3 is centred on the adoption and enhancement of the integrated ACT4CAP27 toolbox, while promoting community building. The establishment of a data and model portal will provide an interactive and user-friendly platform for exploring project data and model scenario results (WP4). Additionally, analytical capacities will be built up (e.g. the Agri-Food Modelling Young Researchers' Network) through trainings and workshops (WP5).

The ACT4CAP27 Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform is central to the integration of these pillars, and will serve as a space to share and discuss findings with existing model platforms, research communities, and policymakers. More specifically, the Platform will have the following objectives in mind:

- To increase awareness of the short-medium and long term ACT4CAP27 policy scenarios and policy recommendations in Europe amongst regulators, policy makers and programme operators, through co-learning, co-development and co-implementation;
- To motivate key stakeholders and decision-makers at different levels to support adoption of the novel ACT4CAP27 analytical and modelling framework, through liaising with the EC, and exchanging knowledge through the Interactive Roadmap;
- To discuss how to boost the analytical and modelling capacities in agriculture in the EU and Associated Countries.

- To help facilitate communications and reiterate synergies between ACT4CAP27 and other projects funded through and referenced in the Call Topic and across other relevant EU funded and national projects.

This platform will ensure a broad and diverse stakeholder engagement. Stakeholder involvement will be an iterative and foundational process, enabling the integration of varied perspectives on future scenario development, such as baseline and alternative futures.

Figure 2. The ACT4CAP27 Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform

Altogether, the Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform will be an important tool to share the produced knowledge and to help build the capacity of EC staff and policymakers at EU institutions, national, regional, decisionmakers and expert personnel, as well as help other researchers to understand the improvements provided by ACT4CAP27 (see Table 1). Based on impact analyses with the enhanced toolbox the ACT4CAP27 Interactive Roadmap will guide future policy setting, investments in agri-food and wider bioeconomy and define possible trade-offs and synergies between various sustainability dimensions. The Platform will also inform the formulation of strategies and policies directing agriculture and the wider bioeconomy to achieve its economic, environmental, and social policy objectives to be in line with the agri-food policies post 2027.

Table 1. Expected achievements and targeted end-users

Expected outcomes/achievements	Target end-users
Advances in data analyses, economic theory, econometric techniques and simulation models including the capacity to account for a wider coverage of food system (i.e., analyses including upstream and downstream industries to agriculture) and sustainability dimensions (i.e. economic, social (including health),	Policy makers, supporting staff and practitioners (EC, JRC, national governments) Scientific community
Improvements and extensions of existing models used by the EC based on close collaboration among researchers working on simulation models and on econometrics and data specialists	Scientific community

ACT4CAP27 Modular Toolbox for Sustainable Food System Policy Modelling (includes the ACT4CAP27 Data and Model Portal for accessing and exploration of key results).	Policy makers, supporting staff and practitioners (EC, national governments) Scientific community (including early carrier researchers)
ACT4CAP27 Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform	Policy makers, supporting staff and practitioners (EC, national governments) Stakeholders
ACT4CAP27 Interactive Roadmap	Policy makers, supporting staff and practitioners (EC, national governments) Stakeholders

3. TARGET AUDIENCES

3.1. Geographical Coverage

Given the scope of the project, the geographical coverage of the Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform focuses mainly on stakeholders with EU-level involvement, such as umbrella organisations and EU policymakers. Additionally, national-level stakeholders may be included when relevant to ensure a comprehensive approach.

3.2. Stakeholder Categories

To guarantee the success of the project, it is essential to identify the most suitable stakeholders for the ACT4CAP27 Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform, thereby facilitating extensive and diverse stakeholder engagement. The following four categories of stakeholder groups have been identified and will be further elaborated in Section 3.3:

1. Policymakers and decision-makers;
2. Agri-food chain representatives;
3. Civil society;
4. Scientific community.

3.3. Identified Stakeholders

In preparation of the First Stakeholder Meeting, a stakeholder mapping was conducted, resulting in a list of 234 key stakeholders. In the process, the four categories mentioned above were further subdivided into different types of stakeholders (see also Table 2):

1. Policymakers and decision-makers:
 - a. European Commission: representatives from specific directorates within the European Commission, including those focused on agriculture (DG AGRI), climate action (DG CLIMA), growth (DG GROW), and health (DG SANTE).
 - b. Permanent Representation: representatives from the Permanent Representations of the 27 EU MS (mainly Agricultural Attachés).
2. Agri-food chain representative
 - a. Agri-food Associations: representatives from associations representing various sectors of the agri-food industry, from farmers and producers to processors and distributors.
 - b. Organic and Sustainable Agriculture Organisations: representatives from organisations that promote organic farming practices and sustainable agriculture.

- c. Cooperatives and Trade Associations: representatives from cooperatives and trade associations that promote fair practices, collective bargaining, and shared resources within the industry.
- 3. Civil society:
 - a. Non-governmental organisations (NGOs): representatives from NGOs focusing on environmental and social issues related to agriculture and food.
- 4. Scientific community:
 - a. Research and Innovation Institutes: representatives from institutes that are committed to driving research and innovation in the agri-food sector.

Table 2. Stakeholder mapping for the First Stakeholder Meeting

Stakeholder Category	Stakeholder Type	Total Number of Entities Identified	Total Number of Contacts Identified
Policymakers and decision-makers	European Commission	9	30
	Permanent Representation	27	82
Agri-food chain representatives	Agri-food chain associations	13	39
	Organic and sustainable agriculture organisations	2	12
	Cooperatives and trade associations	9	16
Civil society	NGOs	7	38
Scientific community	Research and Innovation Institutes	3	17
Total		70	234

4. STAKEHOLDER ACTIVITIES

A series of stakeholder activities are planned throughout the project to facilitate engagement and collaboration among key actors and decision-makers in the agri-food sector (see Table 3).

The First Stakeholder Meeting took already place in October 2024 and was initially scheduled to review the conceptual framework and discuss a preliminary list of sustainability indicators and the EU’s sustainable food system policies as set out in the Grant Agreement of the project. Instead, the Stakeholder Meeting discussed the assumptions of the baseline scenario and the different options to include in the four fast-track scenarios of the project: Ukraine's potential EU accession, biodiversity futures, health and nutrition, and strategic dialogue regarding the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)¹. This will be followed by online follow-up meetings in April 2025 to assess progress and make necessary adjustments.

The second stakeholder meeting scheduled for October 2025 would have addressed the metrics of sustainable food systems and the design of scenario studies as outlined in the grant agreement. However, the meeting's focus has been revised to encompass the preliminary modelling outcomes of the fast-track scenarios. Further thematic seminars and webinars are scheduled throughout 2026 to address topics including input use, organic farming, consumer diet shifts.

¹ See also Annex I for the agenda and posters of the First Stakeholder Meeting

The Third Stakeholder Meeting in October 2026 will review model scenario outputs, while subsequent meetings will continue to provide a platform for discussion and feedback on project developments, leading to a roadmap and decision-support strategies by the project's conclusion in 2028. Throughout these activities, a diverse group of participants, including policymakers, representatives from the agri-food chain, civil society, and the scientific community, will collaborate.

Table 3. Overview of the stakeholder activities as set out in the Grant Agreement of ACT4CAP27

Events	Date	Content	Stakeholder Category	Related WPs
1 st Stakeholder meeting	Oct 2024	Review assumptions for the baselines and collect feedback on the scenarios proposed for a “fast track” analysis (results to be presented in 2025)	Policymakers; agri-food chain representatives; civil society; scientific community	WP1, WP6
Stakeholder meetings online	Apr 2025	Short follow-up meetings 6 months after the 1 st Stakeholder meeting to discuss progress and possible adjustments.	Policymakers; agri-food chain representatives; civil society; scientific community	WP1, WP6
2 nd Stakeholder meeting	Oct 2025	Review the results of the “fast track” analysis and discuss the design of the next scenario studies.	Policymakers; agri-food chain representatives; civil society; scientific community	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP6
Stakeholder meetings online	Apr 2026	Short follow-up meetings 6 months after the 2 nd Stakeholder meeting to discuss progress and possible adjustments.	Policymakers; agri-food chain representatives; civil society; scientific community	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP6
Thematic seminar/webinar 1	Aug 2026	Input use, organic farming, circular economy.	Policymakers; agri-food chain representatives; civil society; scientific community	WP6 – T6.2
Thematic seminar/webinar 2	Oct 2026	Shift in consumer diets and European Green Deal actions relating to climate and environment/biodiversity/pollution.	Policymakers; agri-food chain representatives; civil society; scientific community	WP6 – T6.2 & 6.4
3 rd Stakeholder meeting	Oct 2026	Review model scenario outputs (baseline and first policy impact results).	Policymakers; agri-food chain representatives; civil society; scientific community	WP6
Thematic seminar/webinar 3	Dec 2026/ Feb 2027	Accession of Ukraine to the EU.	Policymakers; agri-food chain representatives; civil society; scientific community	WP6 – T6.3
Stakeholder meetings online	Apr 2027	Short follow-up meetings 6 months after the 3 rd Stakeholder meeting to discuss progress and possible adjustments.	Policymakers; agri-food chain representatives; civil society; scientific community	WP6 – T6.3

4 th Stakeholder meeting	Oct 2027	Roadmap and decision-support	Policymakers; agri-food chain representatives; civil society; scientific community	WP6
Stakeholder meetings online	Apr 2028	Short follow-up meetings 6 months after the 4 th Stakeholder meeting to discuss progress and possible adjustments.	Policymakers; agri-food chain representatives; civil society; scientific community	WP6

Furthermore, Ecorys will also be responsible for organising the final conference at the conclusion of the project in February 2029. This event will present a synthesis of the project’s main practice-oriented findings, with the objective of increasing visibility, fostering the exploitation of results, and presenting the project to the relevant stakeholders.

5. ANNUAL REPORTS

In addition to organising stakeholder meetings and the final conference, annual reports of the stakeholder activities are foreseen to be published in March 2025, March 2026, March 2027, March 2028 and at the end of the project in February 2029. These reports, each time annexed to this deliverable, will summarise each event, taking into account the comments of the stakeholders on the key outputs of ACT4CAP, and outline the next project steps for stakeholder engagement.

The first annual report, provided in Annex 1, was postponed from March to August 2025 to also integrate the feedback from the spring 2025 meeting to inform the planning for the next in-person autumn meeting in 2025.

6. IMPROVING STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

Some initial lessons learned could be drawn from the First Stakeholder Meeting that took place in person in Brussels on the 23rd of October 2024. In preparation for this Meeting, we contacted over 200 stakeholders, as mentioned in Section 3.3. Ultimately, 35 stakeholders confirmed their participation and only 18 of them were actually in attendance at the Meeting. As a result, there was also an imbalance in the representation of the targeted stakeholder categories, with some categories being under-represented. Low end-users’ engagement was also cited in ACT4CAP27’s Grant Agreement as one of the critical risks. To avoid this in the future, we aim to overbook participants slots to allow for potential no-shows, so we can secure at least 25-30 representatives. Finally, the engagement strategies for different stakeholder groups as outlined in Deliverable 7.2 (Balazs, 2024) could also help to increase a broader participation and ensure a more balanced representation in the planned stakeholder activities.

Additional actions taken and proposed to enhance stakeholder engagement are outlined in the first annual stakeholder engagement report (Annex 1).

REFERENCES

Balazs, K. (2024). Deliverable D7.2 (D21) Communication, Dissemination and Impact Strategy and Plan and Reporting ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe project GA Nr. 101134874.

ANNEX 1.

ACT4CAP²⁷

Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

Stakeholder Engagement Report 2025

12 August 2025

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Abbreviations

ACT4CAP27	Advancing Capacity and Analytical Tools for Supporting Common Agricultural Policies post-2027
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CBAM	Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism
EU	European Union
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

ACT4CAP27 (Advancing Capacity and Analytical Tools for Supporting Common Agricultural Policies post-2027) is committed to maintaining a continuous dialogue with European Union (EU) policy makers and national authorities, as well as other key stakeholders across the agri-food system. This engagement is primarily carried out through the Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform, which facilitates interaction with target audiences and promotes the visibility and uptake of project results.

In 2024, efforts focused on laying the foundations for stakeholder engagement through the development of the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy Plan (Deliverable D7.1). This document sets out the objectives, key stakeholder groups, and planned activities for the duration of the project.

As part of early implementation, two stakeholder events were organised by mid-2025:

- An in-person stakeholder meeting held on 23 October 2024;
- A follow-up online meeting held on 6 May 2025.

This Annual Stakeholder Engagement Report summarises the engagement activities conducted during the year and serves as a tool to assess progress and adjust the engagement strategy as needed. While the October 2024 event was briefly reported in D7.1, lower-than-expected participation prompted a review and update of the stakeholder mapping. Ahead of the May 2025 online meeting, targeted outreach efforts led to improved participation.

Originally scheduled for March 2025, this report was postponed to August 2025 to incorporate feedback from the May event and provide a more complete overview of stakeholder engagement to date. It offers an updated basis for planning the next in-person meeting, scheduled for autumn 2025, and ensures that the engagement strategy remains responsive and inclusive. For the autumn meeting, the key improvement will be to ensure more diverse participation, with a particular focus on strengthening the involvement of agri-food chain associations, NGOs, and national authorities.

1. INTRODUCTION

ACT4CAP27 aims to strengthen analytical capabilities, tools, and collaborative technical infrastructure within the policy modelling community to support evidence-based EU agri-food policies post-2027. It takes a comprehensive food systems approach, building analytical capacity to quantitatively assess the impacts of future policies on the economic, social (including health), environmental, and climate sustainability of food systems.

Stakeholder engagement is a central element of ACT4CAP27, implemented through the Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform. The platform enables continuous dialogue with key stakeholders while also increasing the visibility of the project and its results among a broader audience. Specifically, it aims to:

- Inform stakeholders about ACT4CAP27 policy scenarios and recommendations to enhance understanding and encourage informed decision-making.
- Engage stakeholders to contribute their knowledge, refining project outcomes and ensuring that model results align with practical policy needs.
- Motivate stakeholders to support the ACT4CAP27 analytical and modelling framework.

To guide this process, a dedicated Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (Deliverable D7.1) was developed, outlining the objectives of engagement, the key target audiences, and planned activities. Based on this strategy, the project includes a series of stakeholder engagement activities: four in-person meetings, four online meetings, and three thematic webinars, scheduled between 2024 and 2028 (see also Figure 1). These activities are aligned with major project milestones, providing timely opportunities for stakeholder input on draft outputs, scenario development, and modelling assumptions. The process will conclude with a final conference in early 2029, bringing together all key actors to reflect on outcomes and support the integration of ACT4CAP27 insights into future EU agri-food policy.

Figure 1. Overview of stakeholder activities in ACT4CAP27

As part of ACT4CAP27’s ongoing efforts to strengthen stakeholder engagement, annual stakeholder engagement reports are produced to document progress and inform future actions. This report presents a short summary of the engagement activities carried out at the end of 2024 and beginning of 2025, capturing key discussions, stakeholder feedback on project outputs, and suggestions for improvement. It also outlines the next steps planned to deepen engagement and maximise the relevance, usability, and uptake of ACT4CAP27 results.

2. STAKEHOLDER ACTIVITIES OVERVIEW

2.1. First Stakeholder Meeting – 23 October 2024 (Brussels)

The first stakeholder meeting brought together approximately 35 participants, from which 17 external stakeholders, for an in-person session in Brussels. A summary of engagement tools, participant representation, key takeaways, and lessons learned is provided in Table 11, while the full agenda is available in Annex 1.

The event focused on two core objectives:

- Discussing the ACT4CAP27 baseline scenario, including its narrative and assumptions.
- Initiating the co-design of four “fast-track” scenarios: Ukraine’s European Union (EU) accession, biodiversity futures, health and nutrition, and the strategic dialogue on the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).

Participants engaged in in-depth discussions on scenario assumptions such as the adoption rate of eco-schemes, digital innovations, and projected trends in meat consumption. They also identified key policy considerations for the baseline, including the Nature Restoration Law, EU Deforestation Regulation, and the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM). A poster session allowed stakeholders to contribute ideas for the design and policy focus of each fast-track scenario. Topics discussed included Ukraine’s accession, biodiversity futures, policy options for addressing sugar intake, and the strategic dialogue and the CAP.

The meeting reinforced the need to align ACT4CAP27’s modelling work with ongoing EU policy developments and highlighted opportunities for incorporating stakeholder insights into scenario design and assessment frameworks.

Figure 2. First stakeholder meeting in Brussels, 23 October 2024

2.2. Online Stakeholder Consultation – 6 May 2025

Held virtually, the second consultation convened nearly 60 participants, including researchers, policymakers, and NGO/agri-food representatives from across Europe. The focus was forward-looking, exploring stakeholder perspectives on the post-2027 CAP architecture and support

systems. A summary of engagement tools, participant representation, key takeaways, and lessons learned and feedback is provided in Table 1, while the full agenda is available in Annex 2.

The event began with an overview of ACT4CAP27’s objectives and an early preview of the *Vision100* paper—a strategic document developed with other Horizon Europe projects, addressing future CAP priorities including result-based payments, nutrient management, competitiveness, and digitalisation.

Participants then joined breakout sessions on:

- Reimagining the CAP architecture: Stakeholders largely supported increasing support for green payments (e.g., eco-schemes) while reducing coupled payments. There was strong interest in simplifying CAP interventions, enhancing result-based approaches, and expanding innovation and investment support.
- The future of CAP support: Discussions addressed eligibility criteria, conditionalities, and the potential for capping payments. Stakeholders advocated for fairer distribution of support, greater subsidiarity, and clearer links between payments and public goods delivery.

Key takeaways included broad consensus on the need to rebalance CAP objectives toward environmental and social goals, strengthen advisory systems, and incentivise innovation. These insights will directly inform the finalisation of scenario assumptions and policy options assessed in ACT4CAP27.

Figure 3. Online Stakeholder consultation, 6 May 2025

Table 1. Overview of past stakeholder activities

Event name	Date	Objectives	Engagement tools	Participant representation	Key take-aways for ACT4CAP27	Key lessons for engagement	Participant feedback
First stakeholder meeting (In person)	23 October 2024	Discussion of baseline scenario and co-design of four fast-track scenarios (Ukraine's accession, Biodiversity futures, Health and nutrition, and the Strategic Dialogue and the CAP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mentimeter Poster session 	<p style="text-align: right;">total: 35</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 18 internal participants 17 external participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aligning baseline scenario across ACT4CAP and other horizon projects (e.g. BrightSpace & LAMASUS) Improve integration of (new) CAP measures into models Revise the fast-track scenario on the Strategic Dialogue and the CAP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Central location supported in-person attendance Broader external representation would strengthen the diversity & relevance of stakeholder input Anticipate for no-shows: slight overbooking helps meet attendance targets Provide an opportunity for feedback 	NA
Online stakeholder consultation (Online, Teams)	6 May 2025	Gathering stakeholder perspectives on post-2027 CAP architecture and support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Eventleaf (registration) Mentimeter Miro boards 	<p style="text-align: right;">total: 60</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 23 internal participants 37 external participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CAP measures should be simplified and offer attractive financial incentives to encourage uptake, with impact strengthened through targeted, measurable, result-based approaches Greater flexibility is needed to adapt support and conditionality to national and local contexts Reflection of whether CAP payments could shift from form-based to function-driven approaches to better capture environmental and social outcomes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smooth registration process via Eventleaf Ensure Teams setup allows all functionality Miro boards effective for written input; some access issues and limited oral exchange Broader stakeholder mapping improved turnout, though representation gaps still limited diversity of stakeholder input Encourage more feedback responses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overall satisfaction of event: 4.0/5 Relevance of content: 4.5/5 Opportunity to share views: 5/5 Clarity of session structure & moderation: 5/5 <p><i>(Based on feedback from 2 participants via post-event questionnaire)</i></p>

3. NEXT STEPS

Based on the insights gained from the first two engagement activities, the next in-person stakeholder meeting, which is scheduled for autumn 2025 in Brussels, will prioritise greater participation from a more diverse range of stakeholders, particularly those from underrepresented groups such as national authorities, agri-food chain associations, and NGOs. Other methods to reach stakeholders, including personal invitations and a LinkedIn post that can be shared, could be tested to address previously mentioned representation gaps.

Additional practical improvements will include accounting for potential no-shows by slightly overbooking and reaching out to a wider pool of invitees to meet attendance targets. To strengthen the quality of engagement, mechanisms for collecting feedback could be embedded into the event or offered immediately afterwards to encourage more stakeholder responses.

ANNEX 1: AGENDA FIRST STAKEHOLDER MEETING

Time	Session
8:30-9:00	Registration and welcome coffee
1. Opening Session	
9:00-9:20	Introduction
9:20-9:50	Overview of the ACT4CAP27 project
2. Baseline: Narrative, Assumptions and Modelling Results	
9:50-10:30	Discussion on the assumptions used in ACT4CAP27 baseline to help the team prepare the final baseline scenario of the project
10:30-11:00	<i>Coffee break</i>
3. ACT4CAP27 scenarios	
<i>Poster session to collect stakeholders' views on the topics to be addressed in the ACT4CAP27 fast-track scenarios</i>	
11:00-12:30	Ukraine's accession
	Biodiversity futures
	Health and nutrition
	Strategic dialogue and the CAP
4. Next Steps	
12:30-13:00	Conclusions, next steps & closing remarks
13:00-14:00	<i>Lunch</i>

ANNEX 2: AGENDA ONLINE STAKEHOLDER CONSULTATION

Time	Session
1. Opening Session	
14:00-14:10	Welcome and opening remarks
14:10-14:30	Introduction to ACT4CAP27 – Overview of objectives, policy scenarios and progress
2. Setting the Scene: Post-CAP27 Vision	
14:30-14:50	Unpacking the Vision100 Paper – Insights of past model-based policy impact assessments
3. Stakeholder Perspectives on the Post-CAP27 Vision	
<i>Participants will be split into parallel breakout groups and will successively discuss:</i>	
Breakout groups	14:50-15:15 Reimagining the CAP Architecture – What would stay, shift or go? What should decrease/increase?
	15:15-15:20 <i>Break</i>
	15:20-15:50 The future of CAP support – Who gets what, and for which purpose?
15:50-16:15	Plenary session – Breakout groups present their insights and priorities for the future
4. Next Steps	
16:15-16:30	Conclusions – Key take aways and expectations for the next Stakeholder Meeting in Brussels (Autumn 2025)

Possessio

<https://act4cap27.eu>

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101134874>

<http://tinyurl.com/ACT4CAP27OpenAIRE>